

DESIGN, FABRICATION AND TESTING OF LOCUST BEANS PULP WASHER

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ABSTRACT

This study is on the development of a mechanized technology that can effectively wash the yellowish pulp from the locust bean seeds since the traditional method of washing the locust bean seeds from the yellowish pulp is time consuming and tasking due to the sliming nature of the yellowish pulp whenever it comes in contact with water. The designed machine consists of a sieve and a set of paddles and brushes which provides the agitation and abrasion required to depulp the soaked bean seeds, a frame, a transmission system and a prime mover. The soaked seeds are fed into the cylinder with water during operation. The yellowish pulp is discharged after cleaning and the seeds retained on the sieve and later collected through the sieve outlet, after discharging the water in the machine through an opening at the base. Three levels of soaking time (15, 20, 25 mins) corresponding to three levels of locust bean moisture contents (12, 12, 22% wb) and shaft speed of (252, 260 and 264 rpm) was used during preliminary test. The maximum cleaning efficiency of the machine obtained was 87% at 22% wb moisture level and 264 rpm operating speed. The machine is found suitable for commercialization and adoption by locust beans processors to reduce the associated drudgery and boost their income.

KEYWORDS: Depulping, Design, Efficiency, Locust beans, Soaking time,

1. INTRODUCTION

Locust beans (*Parkia biglobosa*) has to be depulped in order for the seeds to be processed into various products, Musa (1991) reported that the locust beans tree can start bearing fruits as from five to seven years after planting, it begins to fruit as from the month of December to March of the year and the fruits ready for harvest as from the month of April. the pods have a tough pericarp; these pods contain yellow powdery pulp in which seeds are embedded, the seeds have hard, black testa making them less vulnerable to insects and rodent infestation (Oladele et al., 1985, Oyewole et al., 1986).

According to Adewumi and Igbeka (1996), the seeds are encased in a tough, elastic and relatively thick coat that has a very low permeability. The low permeability restricts free and easy movement of water through the coats. Interface adhesive force binding the coat to the seed is relatively high. This makes dry hulling of locust bean seed difficult and inefficient. Most of the beans are shattered

when dehulled in a dry condition. Depulping of locust bean is an essential operation after threshing when processing locust bean seeds to its various derivatives and products (Olaoye, 2011).

The traditional method of depulping the beans is by the use of perforated calabash and woven basket. The threshed locust beans are placed in the basket and submerged in a flowing river stream or pond for soaking and depulping. The mixture of the seeds and pulp is stirred with hands and the slurry washed out through the pore spaces while the basket or calabash is being agitated in a flowing water medium. The pulp is washed into the water and the seeds are retained inside the calabash or basket. This operation is labour intensive and time consuming. These method of de-pulping locust bean seeds also requires large volume of water and the ease of de-pulping is a function of availability of water and strength of the individual, Olaoye (2011)

Ajayi (1991) developed a thresher for shelling the pods of locust bean in order to obtain the seeds for further processing. The sheller has a polisher with an abrasive surface; and a blower for the separation of the clean seeds from the pulp and other particles. The machine has a capacity of 9.52 kg/hr of polished and clean seed. Olaoye (2011) also developed a small scale equipment for depulping locust beans seeds. The machine comprises of a vertical cylindrical tank, cylindrical sieve and a vertical rotating shaft which carries both the paddles and brushes. The machine has a capacity to depulp 10 kg of locust bean seed during a unit batch operation. But the existing developed technologies for depulping locust beans are limited in capacity and efficiency. Therefore, this work seeks to design and fabricate a more efficient and high capacity depulping machine that is powered by a petrol engine for adoption in rural areas where the plant grows in the wild.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The construction materials were sourced locally and their suitability, durability and availability was also taken into consideration.

2.1 Description and operating principle of the Machine

The machine shown in plate 1 works by the principle of abrasion, it consists of a sieve and a set of paddles and brushes which

provides the agitation and abrasion required to depulp the soaked bean seeds. This arrangement is mounted on angle bar for support. The paddles are attached to the gear through a shaft that connects the assembly to the prime mover. The soaked seeds are fed into the cylinder with water during operation. The yellowish pulp is discharged after cleaning and the seeds retained on the sieve and later collected by opening the sieve door after discharging the entire water through an opening at the base of the machine.

2.2 Design of the components in the machine

2.2.1 Volume of the depulping drum

The volume of the cylinder was calculated to avoid over feeding of the machine during operation using

$$V = \pi r^2 h \quad (1)$$

Where;

V = volume (m³),

r = radius and

h = height

V₁ which is the volume of the outer cylinder and was calculated to be 0.589 m³

V₂ the volume of the inner perforated washing cylinder and was calculated to be 0.085 m³.

Figure 1. Isometric drawing of the Locust bean depulping machine

2.2.2 Power requirement determination

Power required to operate the machine is given by equation 2 (Hibbeler, 2011).

$$P = \frac{2\pi NT}{60}$$

Where,

P = Power requirement of the machine

N = Speed of shaft, rpm

T = Torque on the shaft, Nm

Equation 3 was used for determining the load due to the paddles, locust bean seeds and the friction of the water that must be overpowered by the prime mover during operation of the machine.

$$F = W = mg$$

Where,

F = force, N

W = weight, N

M = mass, Kg

g = acceleration due to gravity, m/s²

Total load to overcome by the prime mover = $W_p + W_B + W_L + F_w$ (4)

W_p = weight of paddle, N

W_B = weight of brush, N

W_L = assumed weight of locust bean seeds, N

F_w = assumed water friction, N

Density equation in 5 was used to determine the mass of the cylindrical paddles for calculation of their weight.

$$\rho = \frac{m}{v} \quad (5)$$

Where,

ρ = density, kg/m³,

M = mass, kg,

V = volume, m³,

The volume of cylindrical paddle was determined using equation 6.

$$V = \pi r^2 h = \pi \left(\frac{d}{2}\right)^2 h = \frac{\pi d^2 h}{4} \quad (6)$$

The torque developed by the paddles was calculated using equation 7 (Shittu and Ndrika, 2012).

$$T = Fr \quad (7)$$

Where,

T = torque, Nm

F = total load to overcome by the prime mover, N

r = perpendicular distance of the paddles from the shaft, m

Then, using N = 550 rpm (Olaoye, 2011) and substituting in equation 2,

The required power, P = 926.82 watts (safety factor of 2 inclusive)

2.2.3 Shaft design

The required diameter of the shaft to transmit the operating power without failure was determined by using the ASME code equation (Khurmi and Gupta, 2005) for solid shaft design, equation 8.

$$d^3 = \frac{16}{\pi S_s} \sqrt{(k_b M_b)^2 + (k_t M_t)^2} \quad (8)$$

Where

S_s = Allowable shear stress, N/m²;

K_b = Combined shock and fatigue factor applied to bending, Nm;

M_b = Bending moment, Nm;

K_t = Combined shock and fatigue factor applied to torsional moment, Nm;

M_t = Torsional moment, Nm.

Since the solid shaft is subjected to little or no axial loading, the maximum bending moment, M_b is considered to be 0Nm.

After substituting in equation 7,

The required shaft diameter was calculated to be 13 mm.

2.3 Preliminary Machine Testing

The machine in plate 1 was fabricated and tested at the Engineering and scientific services department workshop in NCAM. Three levels of soaking time (15, 20, 25mins) corresponding to three levels of locust bean

moisture contents (12, 12, 22%wb) and shaft speed of (252, 260 and 264 rpm) was used during the preliminary test. Plates 2 and 3 shows the soaked locust beans before depulping and the product after using the machine to depulp the soaked locust beans.

Plate 1. Pictures of the completed machine

Plate 2. Picture of the soaked locust beans pulp before cleaning

Plate 3: Picture of the locust beans after cleaning

2.3 Calculation of Test Parameters

The Depulping efficiency of the machine was determined using equation 9 by Olaoye (2011)

$$De = \left(\frac{M_{cs}}{M_{ui}} \right) \times 100 \% \quad (9)$$

Where, M_{cs} = Mass of cleaned seed (a clean seed is considered to have more than $\frac{3}{4}$ of the seed surface

exposed and devoid of locust bean pulp.

M_{ui} = Mass of material collected at the seed outlet of the depulping machine discharge outlet.

The moisture content of the samples was determined using equation 10 by AOAC (2006).

$$MC_{wb} = \frac{W_i - W_d}{W_i} \times \frac{100}{1} \quad (10)$$

Where,

MC_{wb} = moisture content, wet basis, %.

W_i = initial weight of sample, g

W_d = dried weight of sample, g, is the weight obtained after the sample has been subjected to drying in the moisture Analyzer until the weight of the sample remained constant.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents independent variables considered in the preliminary machine testing and dependent parameters

Table 1. Independent variables considered in machine testing and dependent parameter

S/N	Measured Quantity	Sample		
		A	B	C
1.	Mass of sample fed,(kg)	4.00	8.00	12.00
2.	Moisture content reading, (%)	12.30	12.30	21.90
3.	Soaking time (mins)	15.00	20.00	25.00
4.	Starting time	12.41	1.00	1.15
5.	Stop time for cleaning	12.50	1.11	1.29
6.	Operation time (mins)	9.00	11.00	14.00
7.	Operating speed of the machine without load (rpm)	342.50	342.50	342.50
8.	Operating speed with load (rpm)	252.08	260.01	264.01
9.	Volume of water used in (lts)	16.00	24.00	36.00
10.	Depulping efficiency,%	82.60	83.30	87.00

From the results in table 1, the depulping efficiency of the machine ranges from 82.6-87.00% at an operating speed that ranges from 252-264 rpm and moisture content level ranging from 12-22% wb. The maximum depulping efficiency of the machine obtained was 87% at 22% wb moisture level and 264 rpm operating speed.

Factors affecting the efficiency of the machine are soaking time, volume of water in the machine and the operating speed. Depulping efficiency increases with increases in soaking time, volume of water in the depulping chamber and the operating speed. This trend is in agreement with Olaoye (2011).

4. CONCLUSION

A machine for washing of locust bean pulp was designed, fabricated and preliminary performance test carried out. The materials used for fabricating the machine were sourced locally to enhance affordability. The preliminary test was done at three levels of soaking time (15, 20, 25mins) corresponding to three levels of locust bean moisture contents (12, 12, 22%wb) and operating speed of (252, 260 and 264 rpm). The depulping efficiency of the machine ranges from 82.6 – 87.00% at an operating speed that ranges from 252 - 264 rpm and moisture content level ranging from 12 – 22% wb. The maximum depulping efficiency of the machine obtained was 87% at 22% wb moisture level and 264 rpm operating speed. Factors affecting the efficiency of the machine were soaking time, volume of water in the depulping chamber and the operating speed. The result revealed that the depulping efficiency of machine increased with increase in soaking time, volume of water in the depulping chamber and the operating speed.

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